

Integrated pest management—weeds

Effect of nitrogen uptake by weeds on rice yield

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Nitrogen use efficiency in rice is low when weeds compete; that reduces rice yield. Farmers need an economic threshold, when weed control practices would be profitable. We experimented with different weed populations in rice in Joydebpur in 1988 and 1990.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 1 m². Thirty-day-old BR23 seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Weeds were allowed to grow with rice from the 2- to 3-leaf stage at eight weed densities (unwanted weeds were removed). Recommended fertilizer for transplanted aman (wet season second crop) rice was applied.

At maturity, weeds were removed, cleaned, and identified. Weed dry weights and N uptake were determined. Rice grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Fimbristylis miliacea was the dominant weed species, followed by *Sphenoclea zeylanica*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Scirpus mucronatus*, and *Heteranthera limosa*.

Best fit regression models based on average data were used to determine N uptake and yield loss of rice at different weed densities.

As weed density increased, the weeds took up more N and rice less (Fig. 1). This was reflected in grain yield (Fig. 2). Yield losses were 13% with 20 weeds/m² and 17% with 40 weeds/m². □

1. Effect of weed density on N uptake (kg/ha) by weeds and rice.

2. Effect of weed density on rice grain yield.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Crushing snail eggs with a “snail egg clapper”

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The golden apple snail *Pomacea lineata* Spix. is a major rice pest in the Philippines. It can cause total destruction of germinating rice seedlings and more than

20% damage in young seedlings. It can be controlled with organotin molluscicides, but these chemicals are toxic to human beings, livestock, and aquatic life.

Use of a snail-egg clapper.

Other control measures include installing screens on water inlets, releasing snail-feeding ducks in field, and manually collecting and crushing snails and egg masses. Using a snail collector or *salaan* speeds collection of snails and eggs.

Snails lay eggs in clusters on objects above the water surface, including the vegetation of standing crops. Each cluster may contain 25-500 of the delicate eggs. Picking up snail eggs regularly is an effective control measure, but is tiring because it requires stooping.

The snail egg clapper was developed at IRRI to allow egg clusters on rice plants and vegetation to be mashed without stooping. The simple device weighs about 800 g (see figure). When the rope is pulled, the clappers move apart; when it is released suddenly, the clappers snap back together. The strength of clapper impact can be adjusted by tightening the rubber spring.

To operate the device, open the clappers by pulling the rope and align them on the rice plant or vegetation until the egg mass is between them. Then release the rope. The clapper will destroy the egg mass.

We compared the effectiveness of the clapper, collector, and hand picking. Area covered and work rate (egg masses removed/min) were recorded.

Area covered by the clapper varied from 1.6 to 9 m²/min, 35-70% higher than that of the egg collector and 5-10% higher than hand picking.

The work rate of the clapper (mean 20.3/min) was about 1.8 times higher than with the egg collector (mean 11.2/min). With the egg collector, more than 32% of the egg masses dropped off the plant or bounced off the tool. The clapper missed fewer than 4% of the egg masses. We also found that while using *salaan* egg collector, the tillers would

bend under the collector and sometimes needed support as the eggs were scraped off.

Effects of clapper impact on rice plant growth was measured at two growth stages, 3 wk after seeding and at panicle initiation, in collaboration with physiologists. The rice plants used were not infested with snail eggs.

The clapper was set at two levels of impact: high (47.5 g) and low (25.6g). There was no significant difference in plant height, weight of plant, root and shoot weight and their ratio, number of panicles, and grain weight between plants on which clappers were used and untreated plants.

The snail egg clapper is simple and inexpensive (costs less than US\$ 2 to construct), and can be made with locally available materials. Blueprints are available free from IRRI Agricultural Engineering Division. □

Farmingsystems

Hybrid rice ratoon exploited in Sichuan China

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About 0.7 million ha of rice is grown at 29-31°N latitude, below 400 m elevation, in southeast Sichuan Province, China. Annual temperature is 17.5-18.5°C and annual rainfall about 1,000 mm. Most rice areas are rainfed lowland fields planted to a single crop of medium- to long-duration hybrid rice. The growing season is not long enough to grow two crops of rice.

Field duration of the rice crop is only 120 d from mid-Apr to mid-Aug. During the rest of the year, the fields are fallow under submergence, or more than 60 d elapse from the harvest of rice to the sowing of wheat in a rice - wheat cropping pattern.

Since 1986, about 80% of the farmers who ratoon rice follow the system rice -